

Records of *Neurothemis nesaea* from Sulawesi, with taxonomic annotations on the *N. intermedia*-group (Odonata: Libellulidae)

Malte Seehausen¹ & André Günther²

¹ Museum Wiesbaden, Naturhistorische Sammlungen, Friedrich-Ebert-Allee 2, 65185 Wiesbaden, Germany; <malte.seehausen@museum-wiesbaden.de>

² Naturschutzinstitut Freiberg, B.-Kellermann-Str. 20, 09599 Freiberg, Germany; <andre.guenther@ioez.tu-freiberg.de>

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Abstract. Several specimens of *Neurothemis nesaea* from Central and South Sulawesi were examined. This species hitherto was only known from the original description. Figures of both sexes, annotations concerning the habitat and the type specimens are given (two syntypes deposited at SMF and one at ZMH). For comparison, figures of the wings of *N. intermedia intermedia* (holotype is deposited at RBINS), *N. intermedia atalanta* (two syntypes are deposited at NMS) and *N. intermedia excelsa* are provided, as well as figures of *N. degener* (three syntypes are deposited at RBINS). *Neurothemis degener* is not associated with *N. intermedia* but considered to represent a full species. *Neurothemis septentrionis* (holotype is deposited at UMMZ) is synonymized with the nominate subspecies of *N. intermedia*.

Further key words. Dragonfly, Anisoptera, *Neurothemis degener* stat. nov., *Neurothemis septentrionis* syn. nov., morphology, taxonomy

Introduction

During recent studies of the genus *Neurothemis* Brauer, 1867 by SEEHAUSEN & Dow (2016), several specimens were examined collected by the second author (AG) in Sulawesi, Indonesia. This collection includes four specimens of *Neurothemis nesaea* Ris, 1911, a poorly known species which was so far only known from the original description of two males and a female collected by Hans Fruhstorfer at 'Lompa battau' in South Sulawesi. LIEFTINCK (1934b, 1953) considered *N. nesaea* to be the easternmost subspecies of the closely related *Neurothemis intermedia* (Rambur, 1842), which was described from a single male collected in Bombay, India. In the IUCN Red List assessment KALKMAN (2009) indicates the need for a revision of the genus to determine if *N. nesaea* is a valid species. Thus we used this opportunity

to examine the relationship of the Sulawesi taxon with the *N. intermedia*-group. We searched for further specimens of *N. nesaea* in several Museum collections and compared them with the type specimens of *N. nesaea* as well as with specimens of *N. intermedia intermedia*, *N. intermedia atalanta* Ris, 1913, *N. intermedia excelsa* Lieftinck, 1934 and with the rare and poorly known *N. intermedia degener* (Selys, 1879). The known range of all taxa appears to be clearly definable: *Neurothemis nesaea* is endemic to Sulawesi, *N. intermedia intermedia* occurs from Sri Lanka throughout India to Nepal, *N. intermedia degener* occurs from East India towards southern Myanmar, *N. intermedia atalanta* from East India across Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, and Cambodia towards Vietnam, and *N. intermedia excelsa* is restricted to the islands of Java, Kangean, and Sumba. Because the range of three subspecies of *N. intermedia* is stated to overlap in East India we also examine their relationship, characters, and the classification.

Material and methods

Specimens of *Neurothemis nesaea*, including the type specimens, were examined and compared with specimens of *N. intermedia intermedia* from Sri Lanka, India and Nepal (n=45♂, 34♀; held in BMNH, MWNH, RBINS, SME, UMMZ, ZMB, ZMH & ZSM), *N. intermedia degener* from India and Myanmar (n=15♂, 6♀; held in RBINS, RMNH & ZSM), *N. intermedia atalanta* from India, Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, and Cambodia (n=11♂, 9♀; held in BMNH, NMS, RBINS, ZFMK & ZSM) and *N. intermedia excelsa* from Java (n=14♂, 8♀; held in RMNH & ZSM). The main focus was comparing the male vesica spermalis and characters of the male and female wing venation and marking. Several vesicae spermales were prepared using a 10% potassium hydroxide solution (KOH); dried medial processes are slightly different from illustrations of this study.

Abbreviations used:

Tot – total length; Ab – abdomen; Hw – hind wing; Fw – fore wing; Pt – pterostigma.

Collections with material examined:

AG – Private collection André Günther, Germany

BMNH – The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom

MWNH – Museum Wiesbaden, Landesmuseum für Kunst und Natur, Germany

NMNH – Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Washington, USA

NMS – National Museum of Scotland, Edinburgh, United Kingdom

RBINS – Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Brussels, Belgium

RMNH – Naturalis Biodiversity Center Leiden, The Netherlands

SMF – Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

UMMZ – University of Michigan Museum of Zoology, Ann Arbor, USA

ZFMK – Zoologisches Forschungsinstitut und Museum Alexander Koenig Bonn, Germany

ZMH – Zoologisches Museum Hamburg, Germany

ZMB – Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universität Berlin, Germany

ZSM – Zoologische Staatssammlung München, Germany

Review of *Neurothemis nesaea* Ris, 1911

(Figs 1–4)

Material studied

Type material. 2♂, March 1896, S. Celebes, Lompa-Battau, 3000', leg. H. Fruhstorfer (No. 25920 & 25921); syntypes of *N. nesaea* Ris, 1911, deposited at SMF (Fig. 4). 1♀, March 1896, S. Celebes, Lompa-Battau, 3000', leg. H. Fruhstorfer; syntype of *N. nesaea* Ris, 1911, deposited at ZMH.

Further material (30♂ 20♀). INDONESIA, Sulawesi: 2♂ 3♀, 01-viii-1975, Toraja, Rantepao, leg. Howard R. Wimmer, NMNH. 1♂, 29-viii-1975, Taraja, near Lemo Village, leg. Howard R. Wimmer, NMNH. 2♂, 28-v-1982, SW Sulawesi, Bantimurung (Ciaker Alam), 200 m a.s.l., leg. M.A. Lieftinck, RMNH. 1♂, 03-vi-1982, SW Celebes, Mt. Lompobatang area, 400 m a.s.l., leg. M.A. Lieftinck, RMNH. 3♂ 3♀, 18-ix-1983, Bantimurung, leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 1♀, 25-ix-1983, Pattunuang asue, leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 2♂, 01-x-1983, Pattunuang asue, leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 1♂ 5♀, 02-x-1983, Biseang Labboro, 275 m a.s.l., leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 1♂ 1♀, 04-x-1983, Biseang Labboro, 275 m a.s.l., leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 6♂ 3♀, 06-x-1983, Biseang Labboro, 275 m a.s.l., leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 2♂ 1♀, 07-x-1983, Pattanuang asue, 250 m a.s.l., leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 1♂ 1♀, 13-x-1983, Bantimurung, leg. Scipio S. Pariwono, RMNH. 3♂, 16-vi-1985, S Sulawesi, E of Maros, rivulet in Bantimurung area, leg. J. van Tol, RMNH. 1♂, 19–23-iv-1991, 10 km W of Maros, surroundings of Bantimurung waterfall, 200 m a.s.l. (5°02'S, 119°40'E), leg. J. van Tol, RMNH. 1♂, 13-iii-1993, Central Sulawesi, Besoa

Valley E of the village Doda, Lore Tengah, Poso ($1^{\circ}43'36''\text{S}$, $120^{\circ}15'19''\text{E}$), 1200 m a.s.l., leg. A. Günther, AG. 1♂, 14-iii-1993, Central Sulawesi, Besoa Valley E of the village Doda, Lore Tengah, Poso ($1^{\circ}43'36''\text{S}$, $120^{\circ}15'19''\text{E}$), 1200 m a.s.l., leg. A. Günther, AG. 1♂, 12-x-1993, 45 km ENE Malili, bay in easternmost part of Danau Matana, near exit to D. Mahalona ($2^{\circ}32'15''\text{S}$, $121^{\circ}28'00''\text{E}$), 450 m a.s.l., leg. J. van Tol, RMNH. 1♀, 15-x-1993, 45 km ENE Malili, bay in easternmost part of Danau Matana, near exit to D. Mahalona ($2^{\circ}32'15''\text{S}$, $121^{\circ}28'00''\text{E}$), 450 m a.s.l., leg. J. van Tol, RMNH. 1♂ 1♀, 23-vii-1994, Sulawesi Tengah, Pendolo, swampy grassland near Lake Poso ($2^{\circ}04'13''\text{S}$, $120^{\circ}40'47''\text{E}$), leg. A. Günther & F. Randow, AG.

Figure 1. Known localities of *N. nesaea* in Sulawesi. Map: Sadalmelik, CC-BY-SA-3.0

Diagnosis

Both sexes of *N. nesaea* have dark lateral markings on the abdomen almost continuous (Figs 2d, 3c). The male abdomen varies from yellow to red due to age while the abdomen of the female is yellow.

The dark amber wing coloration of male *N. nesaea* varies (Figs 2a–c). Usually it extends from around the triangle to two cells proximal of the nodus in the Fw and to three cells proximal of the nodus to around the nodus in the Hw, with its distal margin convex in the Fw and curving towards the wing base to different degrees in the Hw. The distal margin is usually diffuse but in some males it is well defined. The wing coloration reaches the posterior wing border around the triangle in the Fw and around the anal loop in the Hw. Five males have a wing coloration reaching up to three or four cells distal of the nodus in both wings. A yellow subcostal and costal area is not presented in *N. nesaea*.

Figure 2. *Neurothemis nesaea* male: a–c – three wing colour variations; d – abdomen lateral and dorsal; e – vesica spermalis, medial process lateral and ventral (after KOH-treatment). Illustrations: MS

The wings of *N. nesaea* females (Figs 3a, b) are similar to those of the males. The amber wing coloration extends from around the triangle to slightly distal of the nodus, with its distal margin convex in the Fw and curving towards the wing base to different degrees in the Hw. One female has only the wing base of the Hw yellow.

Remarks on type specimens

According to Ris (1911) both type males of *N. nesaea* are from the Selys collection, which is deposited at RBINS, and the type female is deposited at ZMH. WEIDNER (1962) listed *N. nesaea* as missing in the collection of ZMH but we found this specimen sorted under *N. intermedia*. This female of *N. nesaea* was labelled in 1906 by F. Ris as »*N. intermedia* race C«, thus Ris' first thought was to treat it as a subspecies but subsequently he described it as a new species. The syntype males were believed lost since they could not be found at RBINS. However during studies of *Neurothemis* specimens in Ris' collection, held at SMF, they were rediscovered there. They were marked, but never published, as »Lectotype« and »Paralectotypoid« by an unknown person. This designation was not valid and as we consider a lectotype designation as not useful, all three specimens are syntypes. They

Figure 3. *Neurothemis nesaea* female: a,b – two wing colour variations; c – abdomen lateral and dorsal; d – vulvar scale. Illustrations: MS

Figure 4. Syntype male of *Neurothemis nesaea* Ris, 1911 with labels (deposited at SMF). Photo: MS

bear labels »S. Celebes, Lompa-Battau, 3000' / III 1896 / Fruhstorfer«. Most likely 'Lompa-Battau' is the Mount Lompobatang, southeast of Makassar in southwest Sulawesi (5.3467°S, 119.9316°E).

Habitat and ecology

Neurothemis nesaea was found in altitudes from 200 m a.s.l. up to 1200 m a.s.l. and we cannot devise a characteristic habitat. The Besoa valley is part of Lore Lindu National Park and characterised by open grassland vegetation and areas of paddy cultivation. It is surrounded by intact montane rainforest and forms an open plain of more than 50 km² on a fluvio-lacustrine terrace. Periodic burning of the grasslands has prevented forest regeneration until today. The considerable age of the open wetlands is a notable feature of the area. The recent records took place in swampy grassland in the floodplain of a small stream. The area was sparsely populated by water buffaloes. Most of the small ponds in the grassland were muddy and created by wallowing buffaloes (Fig. 5). The locality at Pendolo is a semi-cultivated area with swamps, a few muddy ponds due to wallowing buffaloes, and wet grasslands along a small stream close to the mouth in Lake Poso. Jan van Tol collected this species in Bantimurung area along a river running through disturbed forest on limestone with ponds in a semi-cultivated area and at

Figure 5. Wet grassland in the Besoa valley, Central Sulawesi, a habitat of *Neurothemis nesaea* (14-iii-1993). The picture does not show the exact collecting site. Photo: AG

the Danau Matana lakeshore with muddy bottom and trees, incl. *Pandanus* sp. Specimens stored at NMNH were collected in grass and scrubland near rice paddy fields.

Discussion

The differences between the members of the *Neurothemis intermedia*-group and *N. nesaea* are relatively slight as in other members of the genus (cf. SEEHAUSEN & DOW 2016). The main differences between the taxa are the extent of the amber wing coloration and to some extent differences in the density of the wing venation (Tables 1, 2). We are unable to distinctly separate *N. nesaea* and the taxa of the *N. intermedia*-group, except *N. degener*, by using characters of the vesica spermalis. In *N. degener* the medial process of the vesica spermalis is much broader dorsally and has a larger lateral process than in *N. intermedia* ssp. and *N. nesaea*, thus it is closer to *N. fluctuans* (Fabricius, 1793; compare figs 2e, 6a with SEEHAUSEN & DOW 2016: fig. 18b). Also the lateral markings on the abdomen of *N. degener* are short streaks as in *N. fluctuans* while the wing coloration and venation appears intermediate between *N. fluctuans* and *N. intermedia* (compare Figs 6a, b, 11a, b with SEEHAUSEN & DOW 2016: figs 14b–e). Molecular studies may shed

Figure 6. *Neurothemis degener*: wings of male and female; male vesica spermalis lateral; medial process lateral and ventral, after KOH-treatment. Illustrations: MS

Table 1. Sizes and wing venation of males of *Neurothemis intermedia* ssp., *N. nesaea* and *N. degener*.

	<i>N. i.</i> <i>intermedia</i> (n=45)	<i>N. i.</i> <i>atalanta</i> (n=11)	<i>N. i.</i> <i>excelsa</i> (n=14)	<i>N. nesaea</i> (n=32)	<i>N. degener</i> (n=15)
Tot [mm]	34–38	26.5–33	25–30.5	29–34	32–36
Ab [mm]	21.5–25	17.5–21.5	16–19.5	19–22	21–23
Fw length [mm]	26–30.5	20–25.5	18.5–23.5	22–26	26–29
Hw length [mm]	25–29	19–24.5	18–22.5	21–25	25–28
Pt [mm]	3–4	2–3	2–3	2.5–3	3–4
Antenodals Fw/Hw	10,5–13,5/ 9–11	8,5–10,5/ 8–9	8,5–12,5/ 7–9	10,5–12,5/ 8–10	11,5–14,5/ 9–11
Subnodals Fw/Hw	9–11/9–12	7–8/7–9	7–9/7–10	7–11/8–12	8–11/8–11
Cells in triangle Fw/Hw	2–3/2	2/0–2	2/0–2	2–5/2–4	2–3/2
Cells in sub-triangle	3	3	2–3	3–6	3–4
Cross-veins cubi- to-anal-space Fw/Hw (Cux)	2–5/2–3	2–5/1–2	2–4/2–3	3–6/2–4	3–6/2–3
Cell rows of dc-field border- ing Fw-triangle	3–4	2–3	2–4	3–5	3–4
Cell rows radial planate	1	1	1	1	1
Cell rows medial planate	1	1	1	1	1–2

further light on the relationship of *N. degener* with *N. fluctuans* and *N. intermedia* but we presently consider *N. degener* to be a valid species. Three syntypes (2♂ 1♀) of *Neurothemis degener* Selys, 1879 are deposited at RBINS (Fig. 7). We also found that *Neurothemis septentrionis* Förster, 1904 (Fig. 8; deposited at UMMZ), hitherto considered a synonym of *N. degener*, corresponds with the nominate subspecies of *N. intermedia* (holotype deposited at RBINS, fig. 9; also cf. fig. 11a) and not with *N. degener*, thus we introduce *N. septentrionis* as a new junior synonym of *N. intermedia*.

Table 2. Sizes and wing venation of females of *Neurothemis intermedia* ssp., *N. nesaea* and *N. degener*.

	<i>N. i.</i> <i>intermedia</i> (n=34)	<i>N. i.</i> <i>atalanta</i> (n=9)	<i>N. i.</i> <i>excelsa</i> (n=8)	<i>N. nesaea</i> (n=21)	<i>N. degener</i> (n=6)
Tot [mm]	29–36	26–31	25–29	28.5–32	32–34
Ab [mm]	19–23.5	16.5–20	16–18.5	18.5–21	21–22
Fw length [mm]	25–29.5	21–24.5	19–23	23–25.5	28–30
Hw length [mm]	24–29	20–23.5	18–22	22–25	26–29
Pt [mm]	3–4	2.5–3	2–2.5	2.5–3	3–4
Antenodals Fw/Hw	10.5–13.5/ 9–11	9.5–11.5/ 8–9	8.5–11.5/ 7–9	9.5–12.5/ 8–10	12.5–14.5/ 9–12
Subnodals Fw/Hw	9–11/9–11	8–9/7–9	6–9/7–9	8–12/8–11	9–10/9–10
Cells in triangle Fw/Hw	2/2	0–2/2	2/2	2–4/2–3	2
Cells in sub- triangle	3	2–3	2–3	3–5	3
Cross-veins cubi- to-anal-space Fw/Hw (Cux)	3–5/2–3	3–5/2–3	3–4/2	3–6/2–3	4–5/2–3
Cell rows of dc-field border- ing Fw-triangle	3	2–3	2–3	3–4	3
Cell rows radial planate	1	1	1	1	1
Cell rows medial planate	1	1	1	1	1

The comparison of *N. nesaea* with the other taxa of the *N. intermedia*-group indicates similarities especially of *N. nesaea*, *N. intermedia atalanta* (Fig. 10; syntype male and female deposited at NMS), and *N. intermedia excelsa*. In overall size all these taxa are smaller than *N. intermedia intermedia*, and there is no yellow within the subcostal and costal area to the Pt as it is in the nominate subspecies and *N. degener* (Figs 6a, b, 11a–h). The extent of the wing coloration of male *N. intermedia atalanta* and *N. nesaea* overlaps, especially because we have seen males with a diffuse distal margin as well

Figure 7. Syntype male of *Neurothemis degener* Selys, 1879 with labels (deposited at RBINS). Photo: MS

as with a defined distal margin in both taxa (Figs 2a–c, 11c, e). *Neurothemis intermedia excelsa* males differ by having a wing coloration not reaching the triangle in the fore wing and reaching about to the triangle in the hind wing (Fig. 11g). But the common character separating *N. nesaea* from *N. intermedia atalanta* and *N. intermedia excelsa* is the slightly denser wing venation (RIS 1911, 1913; LIEFTINCK 1934a, 1953), especially in the triangles, sub-triangles and the dc-field (Tables 1, 2). RIS (1911) stated that the female vulvar scale of *N. nesaea* extends at right angle to the abdomen. However, during our study we found no reliable character separating females by using the vulvar scale.

We consider *N. nesaea* as a full species and not as a subspecies of *N. intermedia*. We cannot state with confidence whether *N. intermedia atalanta* and *N. intermedia excelsa* both represent subspecies of *N. intermedia* or if at least one of them is a junior synonym of *N. nesaea*. Based on wing pattern and abdominal markings, *N. intermedia atalanta* and *N. intermedia excelsa*

Figure 8. Holotype male of *Neurothemis septentrionis* Förster, 1904 with labels (deposited at UMMZ). Photo: Mark O'Brien

Figure 9. Holotype male of *Libellula intermedia* Rambur, 1842 with labels (deposited at RBINS). Photo: MS

Figure 10. Syntype male of *Neurothemis intermedia atalanta* Ris, 1916 with labels (deposited at NMS). Photo: Richard Lyszkowski

intermedia intermedia

a) male

b) female

intermedia atalanta

c) male

d) female

e) male

f) female

intermedia excelsa

g) male

h) female

Figure 11. Male and female wings of related members of the *Neurothemis intermedia*-group. Illustrations: MS

appear to be closer to *N. nesaea* rather than to *N. intermedia*. At present no taxonomic change is suggested but perhaps molecular analysis will shed further light on the relationships. The taxonomy of the *N. intermedia* group as currently understood is the following:

- *Neurothemis degener* (Selys, 1879) stat. nov.
- *Neurothemis intermedia* (Rambur, 1842)
 - *Neurothemis septentrionis* Förster, 1904 syn. nov.
 - *Neurothemis intermedia atalanta* Ris, 1913
 - *Neurothemis intermedia excelsa* Lieftinck, 1934
- *Neurothemis nesaea* Ris, 1911

Neurothemis nesaea was assessed as »Data Deficient« in IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2009 (KALKMAN 2009). The dragonfly fauna of Sulawesi is still very inadequately investigated but the small number of records suggests that *N. nesaea* is at least very local in occurrence. In a total of eight visits to different parts of Sulawesi, AG has not found the species anywhere else on the island other than in the Besoa valley and near Lake Poso.

Simplified key to *Neurothemis nesaea*, *N. degener*, and *N. intermedia* ssp.

Note: Females are very difficult to separate and this key may not fit for every specimen. Also be aware of *N. fluctuans* when keying *N. degener*.

- | | |
|---|--------------------------|
| 1a – males | 2 |
| 1b – females..... | 6 |
| 2a – Yellow-amber coloration of wing base usually not reaching nodus; if extending to nodus, than lacking a yellow costal area reaching Pt (Figs 2a–c, 11 a, c, e, g) | 3 |
| 2b – Yellow-amber coloration of wing base extending beyond nodus with a yellow tinted costal area reaching Pt (Fig. 6a); East India and Myanmar | <i>N. degener</i> |
| 3a – Without yellow tinted costal area (Figs 2a–c & 11c, e, g); Pt 2–3 mm; usually smaller with a total length of 25–34 mm and Hw length of 18–25 mm | 4 |

- 3b – With yellow tinted costal area reaching Pt (Fig. 11a); Pt 3–4 mm; usually larger with a total length of 34–38 mm and Hw length of 25–29 mm; India and Sri Lanka *N. intermedia intermedia*
- 4a – Wing venation less dense, usually with triangles of Fw/Hw consisting of 2/0–2 cells, sub-triangles of 2–3 cells and dc-field of 2–4 cell rows; coloration of wing base never reaching nodus (Figs 11c, e, g) 5
- 4b – Wing venation denser, usually with triangles of Fw/Hw consisting of 2–5/2–4 cells, sub-triangles of 3–6 cells and dc-field of 3–5 cell rows; coloration of wing base may extend to around the nodus (Figs 2a–c); Sulawesi *N. nesaea*
- 5a – Coloration of the wing base not reaching triangle in the Fw and extending to triangle in the Hw (Fig. 11g); Java, Kangean Islands and Sumba *N. intermedia excelsa*
- 5b – Coloration of the wing base reaching triangle in the Fw and may extend to distal of the triangle in the Hw (Figs 11c, e); East India, Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam *N. intermedia atalanta*
- 6a – Yellow subcostal and costal extending to Pt is present (Figs 6b, 11b); Pt 3–4 mm; usually larger with a total length of 29–36 mm and Hw length of 24–29 mm 7
- 6b – Yellow subcostal and costal extending to Pt is lacking (Figs 3a, b, 11d, f, h); Pt 2–3 mm; usually smaller with a total length of 25–32 mm and Hw length of 18–25 mm 8
- 7a – Wing apices tinted brownish (Fig. 6b); East India and Myanmar *N. degener*
- 7b – Wing apices hyaline (Fig. 11b); India and Sri Lanka *N. intermedia intermedia*
- 8a – Wing venation less dense with triangles of Fw/Hw consisting of 2/0–2 cells, sub-triangles of 2–3 cells and dc-field of 2–4 cell rows; coloration of wing base may at most extend to around the triangles (Figs 11d, f, h); continental Asia, Java, Kangean Islands, and Sumba 9

- 8b – Wing venation slightly denser with triangles of Fw/Hw consisting of 2–4/2–3 cells, sub-triangles of 3–5 cells and dc-field of 3–4 cell rows; coloration of wing base may at most extend to nodus (Fig. 3a, b); Sulawesi *N. nesaea*
- 9a – Coloration of the wing base restricted to innermost cells (Fig. 11h); Java, Kangean Islands, and Sumba .. *N. intermedia excelsa*
- 9b – Coloration of the wing base usually extending to around the nodus but females with less distinct coloration occur as well (Figs 11d, f); east India, Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam *N. intermedia atalanta*

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Addendum (28-x-2016)

While this paper was in press, the following additional records of *Neurothemis nesaea* from Indonesia reached us. All specimens are stored in coll. RMNH and were discovered and kindly communicated to us by Vincent J. Kalkman.

Additional material (3♂ 1♀). INDONESIA, Sulawesi: 1♂, 27-viii-1932, Laika, Towutimeer [Danau Towuti], C. Celebes. 1♂, 02-ix-1932, Timampu, C. Celebes, leg. R. Woltereck. 1♂ 1♀, 25-vi-1936, Poso, Watampone Lorong, 150 m a.s.l., leg. L.J. Toxopeus.